

INTEGRATION OF WEATHER RADAR AND RAIN GAUGE DATA: A STATISTICAL AND GEOSTATISTICAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

For hydraulic-hydrological models to yield results consistent with reality, it is crucial to analyze the quality of the input parameters, aiming to identify any unusual behavior in the data series. Furthermore, combining multiple data sources can be an effective strategy for achieving better results. Combining rainfall estimates from weather radar with surface network measurements can help reduce uncertainties. Data from January, February, March, October, November, and December (rainy months in Brazil's Southeast region) of 2016 from the Camorim Pequeno station in Angra dos Reis – RJ, Brazil, was analyzed for their fit to Log-Normal and Log-Gamma distributions, the presence or not of outliers, the heteroscedasticity or homoscedasticity, and the shape of the cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms. Cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms between radar and automatic tipping bucket rain gauge data were obtained, demonstrating the correlation of these variables, considering a time difference of 5 to 20 minutes between them.

KEYWORDS: Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Grubbs, Goldfeld-Quandt, Cross-covariograms, Cross-correlograms.

I. INTRODUCTION

For flood management, streamflow forecasting has been a widely employed and significant measure in reducing damage, as early knowledge of potential major floods can prevent both material and immaterial losses. A basic type of streamflow forecasting model is based on the rainfall-runoff transformation method. Thus, establishing the appropriate behavior of rainfall series is essential for adequately functioning these models.

The open letter from the Ethos Institute of Brazil [1] points out that climate change "constitutes one of the greatest challenges of our time." This issue has been widely discussed in the media and academic and scientific circles, as reports of natural disasters and extreme temperatures deviating from seasonal patterns are becoming increasingly common. Exceptional rainfall events are responsible for floods and landslides, often resulting in loss of life and/or economic damage. Given this, studies have advanced toward mitigating negative impacts, as the FAPESP Agency [2] points out, stressing the urgency of quick action since many countries have struggled to adapt to climate variations to protect their populations.

Consequently, changes in precipitation have direct implications for other parts of the hydrological cycle, affecting both surface runoff and aquifer recharge. Hydrological models serve as supporting tools for hypothetical scenario studies, helping simulate potential events that may be harmful to society in relation to water regimes while also aiding decision-makers in public policy processes. These findings highlight the need to employ deterministic and stochastic techniques to better describe hydrological processes' regularities and inherent variabilities, aiming to incorporate them into rational proposals for water resource development [3].

This paper is organized into five sections. First, the contextualization of the importance of studying urban floods and how statistics and geostatistics assist in this study were presented. The following

section discusses these topics in detail, highlighting that cities have increasingly suffered from flood-related issues and introducing geostatistics as a fundamental tool for characterizing the correlation between the variables involved in the process. The third section describes the equipment that provided the data used, the radar and the automatic tipping bucket rain gauge, and the statistical tests applied: Kolmogorov-Smirnov, Grubbs, and Goldfeld-Quandt, along with the geostatistical characterization obtained through cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms. Next, the results are presented and discussed, emphasizing satisfactory and unsatisfactory aspects. Finally, section 5 offers a summary of the previous discussions and suggests possible directions for further study.

II. THEORETICAL REFERENCE

The present literature review discusses considerations, concepts, and explanations relevant to studying the behavior of intense rainfall and how geostatistics can be applied to this purpose.

2.1. The growing issue of urban flooding

According to [4], cities consist of highly modified systems where the high population density and issues like soil impermeabilization cause serious environmental problems. Historically, following the Industrial Revolution, soil impermeabilization emerged as the main strategy for urban sanitation and hygiene, aimed at providing healthier living conditions for workers who had migrated in large numbers to urban areas. Today, the urbanization process continues rapidly, leading to excess impermeable surfaces.

One of the leading causes of increased flooding, erosion risks, soil compaction, landslides, and stream and street flooding is impermeabilization [5], as it reduces the soil's water infiltration capacity and increases the potential for surface runoff. Soil covered with cement and asphalt have a high runoff coefficient, causing water to flow intensively over them rather than infiltrate. Combined with the malfunctioning of urban drainage systems, this leads to flooding.

Floods are defined as the gradual overflow of water from the main bed of water bodies onto adjacent floodplains. They are caused by extreme precipitation events, which, when intensified by physical and anthropogenic factors, can have severe material and human impacts on society [6, 7]. In Brazil, 7.4 million people were affected by floods between 2000 and 2018, with 2,457 fatalities recorded and economic losses totaling around 5.3 billion dollars ([8] cited in [9]).

2.2. Geostatistical approach

Geostatistics has been applied in various fields of knowledge beyond mining, where it was initially developed. Examples of this variety of applications include the following studies: monitoring horizontal displacements in landfills [10], mapping soil variability and productivity of sugarcane varieties in the field [11], and filtering bathymetric and altimetric data of a river basin [12].

In the field of hydrology, understanding the spatial and temporal variability of rainfall in hydrometeorological models is a crucial factor when deciding how to adopt an average rainfall for the watershed to be modeled. Geostatistics is a branch of statistics in which quantification errors depend on the relative position between measured and inferred points.

In this geostatistical context, when two or more variables are sampled approximately at the same locations within a given spatial domain and show a significant degree of correlation, cokriging can be applied. This method can be used when the variable of interest is under-sampled compared to the others. This variable is known as the "primary" variable, while the others are called "secondary" variables. The objective is to improve the estimation of the primary variable by using the more densely sampled secondary ones. Verifying the existing correlation between the variables is crucial for cokriging, as this correlation must be strong for the estimations to benefit from using the secondary variable [13].

If $Z_1(x)$ and $Z_2(x)$ are stationary or intrinsic random functions, their cross-variogram is defined by Equation 1. The experimental cross-variogram is defined by Equation 2.

$$\gamma_{Z_1 Z_2}(h) = \frac{1}{2} E[(Z_1(x) - Z_1(x+h))(Z_2(x) - Z_2(x+h))] \tag{1}$$

$$\gamma^*_{Z_1 Z_2}(h) = \frac{1}{2N(h)} \sum \{ [Z_1(x_i) - Z_1(x_j)] [Z_2(x_i) - Z_2(x_j)] \} \tag{2}$$

in which:

$\gamma_{Z_1 Z_2}(h)$ = cross variogram of Z_1 and Z_2 at a distance h ;

$E[\]$ = expected value;

$Z_1(x)$ and $Z_2(x)$ = stationary or intrinsic random functions;

$Z_1(x+h)$ and $Z_2(x+h)$ = stationary or intrinsic random functions located at a distance h from $Z_1(x)$ and $Z_2(x)$;

$\gamma^*_{Z_1 Z_2}(h)$ = experimental cross variogram of Z_1 e Z_2 at a distance h ;

$N(h)$ = number of pairs between the variables Z_1 and Z_2 ;

$Z_1(x_i)$ and $Z_2(x_i)$ = primary and secondary variable, respectively, at position x_i and,

$Z_1(x_j)$ and $Z_2(x_j)$ = primary and secondary variable, respectively, at position x_j .

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Statistical analyses are essential in compiling and interpreting numerical results from experimental work, regardless of the field. They constitute a powerful tool for assessing the adequacy of models to real data. This work is based on several of these analyses, and therefore, the fundamentals of each will be explained below, along with the area of study.

3.1. Radar and rain gauge used

The urban center of Angra dos Reis, where the Camorim Pequeno station is located, is approximately 121 km from the point where the radar Pico do Couto is installed, in the city of Petrópolis, both in the state of Rio de Janeiro (RJ), Brazil. This radar has the following coordinates: latitude -22.4644 (UTM 7514774 m) and longitude -43.2972 (UTM 675205 m) and is at an altitude of 1,760 meters. The Camorim Pequeno station (code: 330010018A) is at latitude -23.005 (UTM 7455745 m) and longitude -44.279 (UTM 573888 m). Figure 1 shows the location of the radar Pico do Couto and the Camorim Pequeno station.

Figure 1. Location of the radar Pico do Couto and the Camorim Pequeno station.

The radar Pico do Couto is managed by DECEA (Department of Airspace Control) and was installed in Petrópolis in the 1990s. This radar provides reflectivity fields at 10-minute intervals. Table 1 summarizes some technical specifications of the radar Pico do Couto. The automatic tipping bucket rain gauge at Camorim Pequeno is operated by Cemaden (National Center for Monitoring and Early Warning of Natural Disasters), with data also provided at 10-minute intervals.

Table 1. Technical specifications of the radar Pico do Couto [14].

Band	S	Range resolution	500 m
Frequency	2.7 to 2.9 GHz	Angular resolution	1°
Wavelength	10.9 cm	Beam width	2°
Power	850 kW	Data resolution	Z, uZ, V, and W
Maximum range	400 km	Rotation	18°/s
Quantitative range	250 km	Scan elevations	0.5 / 1.0 / 1.9 / 2.9 / 3.9 / 4.9 / 5.9 / 6.9 / 7.9 / 8.9 / 9.9 / 12 / 14 / 16 and 18 degrees

3.2. Kolmogorov-Smirnov goodness-of-fit test

The statistical distributions of many atmospheric variables are clearly asymmetric and right-skewed, often due to a physical limit on the left that is relatively close to the data. Precipitation is a variable expected to have this shape, as there can be no negative precipitation [15].

Many continuous distributions are bounded on the left by zero and are positively skewed, including the two-parameters Gamma distribution, which is considered suitable for describing the distribution of precipitation events [16].

To verify the fit of the proposed distribution to the empirical distribution of sample values, goodness-of-fit tests are performed, especially when the probability distribution describing the population from which a certain set of observations was drawn is not known a priori, a situation that frequently occurs in the context of hydrological random variables [3].

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test is generally the most appropriate for continuous distributions. The K-S goodness-of-fit test allows for comparing two data sets without needing those sets to conform to a known distribution function. In other words, it is a nonparametric test [17].

The K-S goodness-of-fit test was applied to analyze the Log-Normal and two-parameters Log-Gamma distributions to provide an initial characterization of the rainfall rate and reflectivity samples. The parameters of the Log-Gamma distribution were estimated using the Method of Maximum Likelihood.

The D, statistic of the K-S test, is the maximum absolute difference between two cumulative distribution functions. To compare a data set $S_N(x)$ to a cumulative distribution function $P(x)$, this parameter is calculated using Equation 3 [17]:

$$D = \max_{-\infty < x < \infty} |S_N(x) - P(x)| \quad 3$$

When the goal is to compare two different experimental cumulative distribution functions $S_{N1}(x)$ and $S_{N2}(x)$, Equation 4 should be used:

$$D = \max_{-\infty < x < \infty} |S_{N1}(x) - S_{N2}(x)| \quad 4$$

in this case, N1 and N2 should be such that the values of x in the two experimental distributions are neighbors.

It is worth noting that, ideally, continuous series should be analyzed; however, this reality is difficult to find in the country, as both rain gauges and radars require constant verification to ensure they are operating correctly and under ideal conditions. Unfortunately, this is not what is observed in practice, leading to operational problems being identified long after they begin, resulting in days or even months

without data reading or with values that do not accurately represent reality. This issue explains some inconsistencies in the results that will be presented and discussed later.

3.3. Grubbs' outlier test

When attempting to fit an empirical distribution to a theoretical distribution, extreme numerical data, known as outliers, can adversely affect the fit. These outliers can result from either an atypical event or an erroneous measurement. Grubbs' test [18] is a methodology for identifying these outliers.

Let the sample of n observations be denoted in increasing order of magnitude as $x_1 < x_2 < x_3 < \dots < x_n$. Let x_n be the questionable value, i.e., the largest value. The test criterion, T_n , recommended by [18] for a single outlier is given by Equation 5:

$$T_n = \frac{(x_n - \bar{x})}{\sigma} \quad 5$$

where \bar{x} is the arithmetic mean of all n values, and σ is the estimate of the population standard deviation based on the sample data, calculated with $n - 1$ degrees of freedom using Equation 6:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}} \quad 6$$

If x_1 , instead of x_n is the questionable value, the criterion is given by T_1 , obtained using Equation 7.

$$T_1 = \frac{(\bar{x} - x_1)}{\sigma} \quad 7$$

The critical value, T_{critical} , is calculated using Equation 8:

$$T_{\text{critical}} = \frac{(N - 1) F_{\text{Student}}^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2N}, N - 2 \right)}{\sqrt{N \left\{ N - 2 + \left[F_{\text{Student}}^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{2N}, N - 2 \right) \right]^2 \right\}}} \quad 8$$

where F_{Student}^{-1} is the inverse cumulative distribution function of Student's t-distribution, N is the number of pairs, and α is the significance level.

3.4. Goldfeld-Quandt's heteroscedasticity test

When the variance of the errors is constant, the data series is said to be homoscedastic; otherwise, it is classified as heteroscedastic. Several tests in the literature aim to identify the presence of heteroscedasticity. Here, the Goldfeld-Quandt's (G-Q) test will be presented, which involves splitting the regression into two: one with values below a certain threshold and another with values above another threshold. A test is then conducted to compare the variances in each regression (a common test for comparing variances, i.e., an F-test). The sample should be divided into three approximately equal parts, and the variances should be compared between the 1st and 3rd thirds using Equation 9. Suppose there is a difference in the variances of the two regressions. In that case, the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity is rejected, and if this is the case, it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity is present, which should be corrected [19].

$$F = \frac{\max(\sigma^2_{1^{\text{st}}\text{thirds}}, \sigma^2_{3^{\text{rd}}\text{thirds}})}{\min(\sigma^2_{1^{\text{st}}\text{thirds}}, \sigma^2_{3^{\text{rd}}\text{thirds}})} \quad 9$$

The variance, σ^2 , is defined by Equation 10:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{\sum (x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2}{n - 2} \quad 10$$

where, x_i is the observed value of the analyzed variable at position i , \hat{x}_i is the estimated value at position i and n is the number of degrees of freedom. To determine whether the sample is homoscedastic or heteroscedastic, the value of F must be compared with F_{critical} calculated using Equation 11; if F is

greater, the test concludes in favor of heteroscedasticity, otherwise, it concludes in favor of homoscedasticity.

$$F_{\text{critical}} = F_{\text{Fisher-Snedecor}}^{-1}(1 - \alpha, n_{1^{\text{st}}\text{thirds}}, n_{3^{\text{rd}}\text{thirds}}) \quad 11$$

where $F_{\text{Fisher-Snedecor}}^{-1}$ is the inverse cumulative distribution function of Fisher-Snedecor, α is the significance level (adopted as 5% in this work), $n_{1^{\text{st}}\text{thirds}}$ is the number of degrees of freedom for the 1st third of the sample, and $n_{3^{\text{rd}}\text{thirds}}$ is the number of degrees of freedom for the 3rd third of the sample.

3.5. Geostatistical characterization by covariograms and correlograms

Covariance indicates whether the association is positive, negative, or absent (null). It calculates the variation of a variable X according to the values of another variable, Y. If the covariance value is greater than zero, there is a positive association; if it is less than zero, there is a negative association; and if it equals zero, the association is null.

However, covariance does not indicate whether the association is strong or weak, as it depends on the scales of the variables. Therefore, correlation is often used, obtained by standardizing the variables. To calculate it, covariance is divided by the product of the standard deviations of X and Y. It is necessary to exclude values from X or Y (depending on which series is lagged or advanced relative to the other) so that all values of X have pairs in Y and vice versa.

When the aim is to check if two variables are correlated with a certain lag or lead, a cross-covariogram should be constructed. Cross-covariance is the covariance between two continuous stochastic processes, where one corresponds to a time instance X_i and the other to a possibly different time instance $Y_{i+\Delta t}$. In turn, cross-correlation is a measure of similarity between two signals as a function of a lag. In the relationship between two time series, one may be related to the other by a step difference [20].

Equations 12 to 17 present the formulas used to calculate the covariogram of X, the covariogram of Y, the cross-covariogram of X and Y, the correlogram of X, the correlogram of Y, and the cross-correlogram of X and Y, respectively.

$$C(X_i, X_{i+\Delta t}) = \frac{1}{N(\Delta t)} \sum_{N(\Delta t)} [(X_i - \bar{X}_i)(X_{i+\Delta t} - \bar{X}_{i+\Delta t})] \quad 12$$

$$C(Y_i, Y_{i+\Delta t}) = \frac{1}{N(\Delta t)} \sum_{N(\Delta t)} [(Y_i - \bar{Y}_i)(Y_{i+\Delta t} - \bar{Y}_{i+\Delta t})] \quad 13$$

$$C(X_i, Y_{i+\Delta t}) = \frac{1}{N(\Delta t)} \sum_{N(\Delta t)} [(X_i - \bar{X}_i)(Y_{i+\Delta t} - \bar{Y}_{i+\Delta t})] \quad 14$$

$$R(X_i, X_{i+\Delta t}) = \frac{C(X_i, X_{i+\Delta t})}{\sigma_{X_i} \sigma_{X_{i+\Delta t}}} \quad 15$$

$$R(Y_i, Y_{i+\Delta t}) = \frac{C(Y_i, Y_{i+\Delta t})}{\sigma_{Y_i} \sigma_{Y_{i+\Delta t}}} \quad 16$$

$$R(X_i, Y_{i+\Delta t}) = \frac{C(X_i, Y_{i+\Delta t})}{\sigma_{X_i} \sigma_{Y_{i+\Delta t}}} \quad 17$$

where C is the covariance, $N(\Delta t)$ is the number of pairs between the two analyzed variables, X_i and Y_i are the values of each variable at time i, $X_{i+\Delta t}$ and $Y_{i+\Delta t}$ are the values at time $i + \Delta t$, \bar{X} and \bar{Y} are the means of the respective variables, σ_{X_i} and σ_{Y_i} are the standard deviations of the variables at time i and $\sigma_{X_{i+\Delta t}}$ and $\sigma_{Y_{i+\Delta t}}$ are the standard deviations at time $i + \Delta t$. Notably, a new mean and standard deviation must be calculated for each time interval, as each different Δt will include or exclude distinct values at the beginning or end of the data series. An important observation about Equations 12 to 14 is that both the index of \bar{X} and \bar{Y} is the letter "i" and not the number "1" as it may appear; this appearance is due to the font design used in the equations.

The Solver tool in MS Excel was used to fit the theoretical cross-covariogram, using the GRG Nonlinear method. GRG stands for Generalized Reduced Gradient; this method works with the gradient of the objective function as input values change and determines that it has reached an optimal solution when the partial derivatives equal zero [21].

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data extracted from the radar contained values outside the valid range for reflectivity readings, which is -32 to 70 dBZ. Therefore, values lower than -32 dBZ and higher than 70 dBZ were excluded before any calculations. A cutoff limit was established for the data series to avoid working with null values or values that could be considered null. This limit was set at 1.2 mm/h for the tipping bucket rain gauge, as it corresponds to the device's minimum detection limit and 20 dBZ for the radar, considering that values above this threshold are those with the highest probability of resulting in precipitation. The reflectivity values in dBZ were converted to mm⁶/m³, and the analyses were conducted using this unit for the radar and mm/h for the tipping bucket rain gauge.

4.1. Kolmogorov-Smirnov goodness-of-fit test

Both rainfall rate and reflectivity data were sorted in descending order. When repeated values were present in the sample (typical case in data from tipping bucket rain gauges), the test was conducted considering the methodology used for samples with repetitions [22]. Table 2 summarizes the obtained values for each theoretical distribution in each month for the D_{max} parameter for rainfall rate and reflectivity.

Table 2. Value of the D_{max} parameter of the K-S test by month and distribution.

Month	Rainfall rate (mm/h)		Reflectivity (mm ⁶ /m ³)	
	Log-Normal	Log-Gamma	Log-Normal	Log-Gamma
January	0.275	0.313	0.102	0.088
February	0.236	0.279	0.102	0.086
March	0.276	0.325	0.124	0.092
October	0.343	0.385	0.071	0.056
November	0.278	0.312	0.087	0.091
December	0.307	0.349	0.114	0.117

The Log-Normal distribution presented the lowest D_{max} for the rain gauge samples. There was no consensus on the reflectivity variable; the Log-Gamma distribution was better for four months, while the Log-Normal distribution was better for two. Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the data's best and worst fit to the Log-Normal distribution for rainfall rate and reflectivity, respectively.

Figure 2. Experimental probability distributions compared with the theoretical Log-Normal distribution for January (best fit) and October (worst fit) rainfall rate data.

Figure 3. Experimental probability distributions compared with the theoretical Log-Normal distribution for October (best fit) and March (worst fit) reflectivity data.

Concerning unsatisfactory adjustments, in the case of rain gauges, which take point measurements, light rain can be deviated due to wind, causing raindrops to fall near the station but not directly on the equipment. Calibration issues in tipping buckets and/or errors in data transmission to the recording computer may also occur. Regarding radars, there can be noise in the transmission and reception of the signal emitted and received by the antenna, poor calibration, and problems caused by horizontal and vertical winds, as well as erroneous readings due to bright banding, hail, discrepancies in raindrop size distribution, attenuation by atmospheric gases, and water running over the protective dome of the antenna [23, 24].

About the outlier test, it was performed for each month; when outliers were identified, they were excluded from the G-Q test and from obtaining the cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms. On average, the rainfall rate series had 361 data points, and the reflectivity series had 121. No data was considered an outlier in February, March, November, and December; in January, one reflectivity data was excluded, and in October, three rainfall rate data were excluded. The significance level used was 0.1. During the research, it was observed that outliers present a particularly delicate issue when dealing with precipitation, more so than with flow rates, due to consistency problems in the database. The decision to exclude such points becomes very challenging, as while they clearly deviate from the trend, there is also the possibility that they represent actual precipitation values that occurred but with a recurrence interval greater than the number of years in the available series. This makes them appear as spurious data, even though they might not be if the series were longer.

4.2. Goldfeld-Quandt’s heteroscedasticity test

Table 3 shows the values of F and $F_{Critical}$ for each month and the test result with a significance level of 0.05. Figure 4 displays the graph with the pairs of values of Log Z and Log R used to verify the homoscedasticity or heteroscedasticity of the data from January; this specific month is presented because it has the most pairs of values.

Table 3. Values of the F and $F_{Critical}$ parameters of the G-Q test and result by month.

Month	Number of pairs	Value of F	Value of $F_{Critical}$	Result
January	148	1.55	1.62	Homoscedastic
February	109	1.26	1.77	Homoscedastic
March	82	1.83	1.96	Homoscedastic
October	65	1.25	2.12	Homoscedastic
November	22	2.87	5.05	Homoscedastic
December	38	1.40	2.82	Homoscedastic

Figure 4. Pairs of values used and results of the G-Q test for January and their residuals.

According to the test, all the values of F were lower than the $F_{Critical}$; therefore, these data exhibit homoscedasticity, validating the procedures used in this study. Although the study focuses on more intense rainfall, excluding lighter rains from the analysis risks compromising homoscedasticity. It is also necessary to consider that the analyzed distribution is not a conventional distribution like the Log-Normal but rather a truncated one.

4.3. Geostatistical characterization by cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms

Considering that the Log-Normal distribution generally proved to be suitable for the data, along with the fact that the Z-R relationships, which correlate radar and rain gauge data, are represented by power relationships of the form $Z = aR^b$, where Z is reflectivity in mm^6/m^3 , R is the rainfall rate in mm/h , and a and b are adjustment coefficients, was opted to create experimental cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms using the logarithms of the reflectivity and rainfall rate variables.

The cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms were calculated for intervals ranging from -60 minutes to +60 minutes in increments of 10 minutes. Negative intervals indicate that the radar recorded values before the automatic rain gauge, while positive intervals indicate that they were recorded after. For each interval, only values with pairs were considered. Based on these new datasets, excluding unmatched data, the mean and standard deviation were calculated only for the remaining data. Graphs were created for each variable individually, and then temporal cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms for both variables together. This procedure was done for both the indicators of whether rain was recorded and for the recorded values themselves. Table 4 presents the highest value of R (Pearson correlation coefficient) for the analysis of indicators and the same analyses for the values themselves.

Table 4. Value of the highest correlation coefficient for indicators and values of the variables by month.

Month	Indicators		Values	
	Largest R	Δt (min)	Largest R	Δt (min)
January	0.64	-20	0.31	-20
February	0.65	-10	0.27	0
March	0.50	-10	0.71	-10
October	0.33	-10	0.38	40
November	0.25	-20	0.89	-60
December	0.39	-10	0.38	30

A difference identified was the interval value corresponding to the highest correlation found when analyzing indicators versus the values of the variable. These small variations can be explained by the differing sizes of the datasets for each group.

Figures 5 and 6 display the cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms - experimental and theoretical - of the indicators and the values of reflectivity and rainfall rate for the months that exhibited better performance. Initially, the theoretical cross-covariogram was adjusted, which allowed for the creation of the cross-correlogram by dividing the covariance values by the product of the standard deviations. However, as explained previously, it is necessary to calculate standard deviations for each time interval. In this case, a single value of the product of the standard deviations was used, referring to the interval with the highest number of pairs.

The adjusted temporal cross-covariogram for the February indicators follows Equation 18, with Δt in minutes:

$$C(I_{Z_i+\Delta t}, I_{R_i}) = C \cdot e^{-\frac{|\Delta t + t_0|}{a}} = 0.03 \cdot e^{-\frac{|\Delta t + 3.58|}{168.83}} \tag{18}$$

where C is the threshold, and a is the range of the cross-covariogram.

Figure 5. Reflectivity and rainfall rate indicators for February.

The adjusted temporal cross-covariogram for reflectivity and rainfall rate values for March follows Equation 19, with Δt in minutes:

$$C(Z_{i+\Delta t}, R_i) = C \cdot e^{-\frac{|\Delta t + t_0|}{a}} = 0.27 \cdot e^{-\frac{|\Delta t + 0.00|}{94.74}} \tag{19}$$

Figure 6. Log of reflectivity and log of rainfall rate for March.

There is a better fit for the theoretical cross-covariogram and cross-correlogram in Figure 5 compared to those in Figure 6, where for the time points 20, 30, and 40 minutes, points are observed that deviate significantly from the expected behavior, which is a progressive decay tending toward zero. This anomaly may result from noise in the radar readings as well as existing failures in the series. Nevertheless, it can be said that the fit was satisfactory. Analyzing the other graphs for the remaining months, it was noted that, on average, the best fits occur when the delay in rain recording by the surface station relative to radar recording is between 5 and 20 minutes; therefore, this can be considered the average time it takes for raindrops to travel 3 km, distance from the CAPPI (Constant Altitude Plan Position Indicator) used to extract the radar data to the surface and reach the rain gauge.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study aimed to analyze rainfall's statistical and geostatistical characteristics measured by a rain gauge and a set of reflectivity data obtained from radar. The adherence of the data to the theoretical Log-Normal distribution and the data's homoscedasticity were assessed. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the Goldfeld-Quandt test proved to be necessary for the primary characterization of the data. Accurately identifying which theoretical distribution explains the dataset and checking whether lower and higher values have similar variances are crucial for concluding with a higher probability of accuracy. It was observed that eliminating data considered outliers in rainfall-related series is a matter that deserves further investigation, as the data may simply not fit within the time interval of the series considered rather than being an outlier in a more extensive series.

After these statistical checks, cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms were developed to investigate how one variable correlates with another. These graphs were not perfect, but they were satisfactory, given that data related to nature presents a great complexity. The methodology of establishing cross-covariograms and cross-correlograms has shown promise. It indicates that the different rain measurement devices correlate through a time delay. It suggests that they should be analyzed in pairs and not at the same instant. This work opens possibilities for evaluating cokriging using radar and rain gauge data for drainage projects, flood forecasts, and alert systems - topics currently under development by the authors.

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